

AA6061 Al-SiC_p Surface MMC's Produced by Laser Processing A Comparison of the Preplacement and Injection Techniques for Introducing SiC_p

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ABSTRACT

Hard particle cladding by laser processing has been developed to create an MMC layer on the surface of aluminium alloys. The preplacement and the injection of the reinforcement phase are the two techniques used in the processing. The present work compares the surface conditions, the microstructures and the wear resistance of the MMC's produced by these two techniques when used for an AA6061 aluminium alloy. The surface MMC layers produced by both techniques showed a significant increase in abrasive wear resistance, compared with the base alloy. The processing parameters and the mechanisms were investigated for both techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Various laser cladding processes have been developed to modify the surface properties of aluminium alloys [1-8]. Hard particles [1, 4-8] have been introduced onto the surfaces of aluminium alloys by either the preplacement or the injection techniques. Compared with the laser processing of other alloy systems [9-14], aluminium has an extremely low laser energy absorption which causes difficulty in the generation of a liquid surface, which is necessary to develop a well incorporated MMC layer on the base alloy. The injection of TiC has been successfully applied to a high silicon Al alloy [1], because the high Si content increased the energy absorption. However, AA6061, which has a low Si content, has attracted much attention as a base alloy in Al MMC's and is therefore of particular interest for applications requiring improved surface properties which might be developed by laser cladding. The preplacement of SiC_p provided sufficient energy absorption for AA6061 alloy, and successfully produced a smooth MMC layer on its surface [4-7]. Unfortunately, the SiC_p preplacement was successful only when the size of SiC_p was 45µm or below [4]. Since a large SiC_p is preferable for a high abrasive wear resistance in an Al-SiC_p MMC [15-16], the injection of SiC_p was investigated [8] as a method of producing an MMC with SiC_p greater than 45µm. The present work compared the laser treated surface conditions, the microstructures and the wear resistance of the MMC's resulting from the preplacement and the injection techniques. Some important factors were discussed for both techniques, including the thickness of the MMC layer, the size of SiC_p and the laser energy density.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

AA6061 Al alloy was the main base alloy used. The composition is Fe 0.21%, Si 0.7%, Mg 1.02%, Cu 0.27%, Mn 0.04%, Cr 0.2%, and Al the balance. The base alloy specimens had a thickness of 6-8 mm. A continuous CO₂ 5kW laser at Culham Laboratory, AEA Technology, Abingdon with a stationary beam producing an annular energy profile was used for the experiments. The specimens were moved under the beam on a work-table to produce all the tracks processed in the present work. The laser beam power q , set at 2.8kW, the radius of the laser beam r_b , 1.0 to 2.5mm, and the velocity of the specimen v , 5 to 30 mms⁻¹ were used in the processing. The laser energy density is given as $E=q/(r_b v)$ (MJm⁻²), referring to the energy intensity [17]. For the preplacement technique, SiC_p (6 and 45μm), or a mixture of 20-60% of the SiC_p and prealloyed AA6061 powder (≤40μm), was blended with an organic solution, and painted on the surface prior to laser scanning. To follow the effect of the thickness of the preplaced layer, this was varied from 30 to 210μm. Pure dry argon gas was used at 50 litres per minute to protect the area scanned by the laser. For the injection technique, SiC_p (≤105 or 150μm), was used as the reinforcement. Three variations were used for the injected materials relative to the surfaces: (1) SiC_p injected on the base alloy surface, (2) a mixture of SiC_p (40%) and AA6061 powder (60%, ≤40μm) injected on the base alloy surface, and (3) this mixture injected onto a preplaced mixture of SiC_p (60%, ≤6μm) and AA6061 (40%, ≤40μm) on the surface. A powder feeder (Plasma Technik, Twin 10C) with a feeding rate 5-10 g min⁻¹ was used for injecting. Pure dry argon gas, through a nozzle of 2 mm in internal diameter, was used to carry and to protect the powder and the laser glazing area against oxidation.

Transverse sections of laser treated specimens were examined using optical microscopy and an estimation of the phase volume fraction was carried out by an image analyzer. Wear tests were carried out on a simple pin-on-disc machine using a constant load of 0.5 kg and speed of 0.236 ms⁻¹. The specimens were cleaned in methanol and blown dry with air before testing against P600 SiC grit paper, which was replaced every 25 m during each test. Weight losses were measured after a known sliding distance by weighing the samples to an accuracy of 10⁻⁵g. All the tests were carried out at room temperature under dry sliding conditions in air.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 THE SURFACE SMOOTHNESS

The laser scanning on preplaced areas produced a smooth surface, Fig.1a, while those developed with the injection technique produced a rough surface, Fig.1b. In the preplacement processing it is most interesting that the overlapped laser tracks did not show a severe surface roughness. A smooth surface can be obtained by overlapping laser tracks only when the same processing conditions are used which produce a smooth surface for a single track.

Figure.1 Typical surface morphologies of (a) preplacement of SiC_p; (b) injection of SiC_p plus AA6061 powder (S for a single track and O for overlapping tracks).

3.2 MICROSTRUCTURES

3.2.1 TYPICAL MMC'S

A surface MMC layer produced by the preplacement technique (SiC_p alone) is shown in Fig.2. SiC_p was well distributed and embedded in the matrix of a smooth and uniformly thick MMC layer which was well incorporated with the base alloy. No cracks and few pores were found in the MMC. Some of the SiC_p particulates partially dissolved and needle particles nucleated on the SiC_p . The needle phase was identified by X-ray diffractometry as Al_4C_3 .

Figure.2 An MMC layer produced by preplacing SiC_p ($6\mu\text{m}$) on AA6061 alloy, laser treated at $q=2.8\text{ kW}$, $r_B=2\text{ mm}$ and $v=10\text{ mm s}^{-1}$. Partial dissolution of SiC_p can be seen.

An MMC layer produced by the preplacement of a mixture (SiC_p +AA6061 powder) is shown in Fig.3. Compared with Fig.2 the thickness of the MMC is significantly increased. A distinctive feature of Fig.3 is that there exist SiC_p free areas in the MMC. These could be attributed to a large average ratio in size ($40/6$) of the AA6061 particle to the SiC_p . When a mixture of $45\mu\text{m}$ SiC_p and the AA6061 powder was used, the SiC_p free areas were not present, Fig.4. A high Si content at grain boundaries, S in Fig.3, is the evidence of the dissolution of small SiC_p .

Fig.5 shows an MMC layer produced by injecting a mixture of $150\mu\text{m}$ SiC_p and AA6061 powder on a surface preplaced with the mixture of $6\mu\text{m}$ SiC_p and AA6061 powder. After laser processing, the injected SiC_p was found to be cracked. This is because SiC_p has a high absorption of laser energy. When SiC_p was laser glazed during injection, the energy absorbed by SiC_p could not be efficiently transferred to the surroundings due to few contacts between SiC_p and AA6061 particles; and therefore the SiC_p heated rapidly. The rapid heating resulted in a dramatic increase in the internal

Figure.3 A $150\mu\text{m}$ thick MMC layer produced by preplacement of a mixture of SiC_p ($6\mu\text{m}$, 60%) with AA6061 powder ($\leq 40\mu\text{m}$, 40%) on AA6061 alloy surface, laser treated at $q=2.8\text{ Kw}$, $r_B=1.5\text{ mm}$ and $v=10\text{ mm s}^{-1}$.

stress of the SiC_p , and the larger the SiC_p , the higher the internal stress level, which was more likely to result in cracks in the largest SiC_p . The amount of energy absorbed by SiC_p will depend also on the position of the SiC_p in the mixture when injected. In other words, the level of energy absorbed by the same size of SiC_p is not uniform. Therefore, only those SiC_p particles, which absorbed a high laser energy, may have cracked. If most of the absorbed energy was transferred to the AA6061 particles, the SiC_p particles may remain intact and have a greater tendency to react with the liquid, giving the dark mottled features (D) seen in Fig.5. The injection of either the SiC_p alone or a mixture of SiC_p with AA6061 powder on

the unreplaced base alloy surface failed to produce a well incorporated MMC. The injection of SiC_p alone required a certain amount of liquid from the base alloy to provide the matrix for the MMC, and agglomeration of SiC_p 's developed, with a large cavity underneath [8]. The injection of the mixture resulted in the MMC separating from the base alloy. This was considered to arise from the extremely low laser energy absorption of the base alloy. A second factor was the

Figure.4 An MMC layer produced by replacement of a mixture of SiC_p ($45\mu\text{m}$, 60%) with AA6061 powder ($\leq 40\mu\text{m}$, 40%) on Al alloy surface, $q=2.8 \text{ Kw}$, $r_B=2.0 \text{ mm}$ and $v=10 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$.

low percentage contact between the SiC_p and base alloy. Thus the generation of the liquid at the surface was insufficient to produce a well dispersed MMC integrated into the base alloy.

Figure.5 An MMC produced by injection of SiC_p ($\leq 150\mu\text{m}$, 40%) and AA6061 powder ($\leq 40\mu\text{m}$, 60%) at 5 gmin^{-1} , on a surface preplaced with SiC_p ($6\mu\text{m}$, 60%) and AA6061 powder ($\leq 40\mu\text{m}$, 40%), $q=2.8 \text{ kW}$, $r_B=1.5 \text{ mm}$ and $v=15 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$.

3.2.2 THE THICKNESS OF THE MMC

For the preplaced SiC_p specimens, the thickness of the MMC layer was controlled only by the thickness of the preplaced layer. The maximum thickness of an acceptable MMC is about $80\mu\text{m}$ [7]. Increasing further the preplaced layer thickness resulted in an MMC layer which was separated from the base alloy by a large cavity generated in the molten zone. The greater the preplaced SiC_p thickness, the larger the cavity. This suggests that the formation of an MMC layer requires a sufficient volume of liquid infiltrating into the preplaced SiC_p layer. The liquid can only be produced from the molten zone below the laser beam, which places restrictions on the volume of liquid available for infiltration of the preplaced layer.

When a mixture of SiC_p and Al powder was preplaced on the surface, the thickness of MMC was increased and the cavity avoided because the liquid phase needed for the matrix of the MMC was provided by the AA6061 powder in the preplaced layer, as shown in Fig.3. However, if a critical thickness of the preplaced mixture was exceeded, porosity in the MMC near to the base alloy was found [4]. It was considered that when the same laser processing conditions were used for a thicker preplaced layer, the energy intensity at the interface between the preplaced layer and the base alloy decreased, because the energy absorbed by the surface depended only on the fraction of SiC_p in the preplaced layer. A thicker preplaced layer absorbed the same

energy but consumed more in melting the powder and in the vaporization of the binder. The volume fractions of SiC_p in the MMC's were estimated via image analysis, having about 60v% for the preplaced SiC_p alone and the original values for the layers produced by the preplaced mixture.

Using the injection technique, increasing the powder feeding rate increased the thickness of the MMC, but the degree of incorporation between the MMC and the base alloy deteriorated. It was considered that when more powder was injected on the surface, the energy absorbed by the injected material increased, but that by the surface decreased. This is because SiC_p has a high laser energy absorption but a low thermal conductivity, and the surface could receive more energy only when the preplaced SiC_p performs as an energy source instead of a heat conductor through which energy is transferred from the injected material to the surface. Therefore, when more powder was injected onto the SiC_p preplaced surface, the surface absorbed less energy because of the less conducting region between the laser and the surface, which was not conducive to the formation of a well incorporated interface.

3.2.3 THE EFFECT OF LASER ENERGY DENSITY

The above discussion suggested that a higher energy input was required to produce a thicker MMC layer in either the preplacement or the injection of a mixture. Therefore, for better understanding and easier control of the process, the effect of the laser energy input must be considered. The energy input is determined by q , r_B and v , and for simplicity, the laser energy density E is used for the following discussion. As observed in previous work [4-7], when the laser energy density was higher than a critical level, defined here as E_{max} , the MMC layer would be broken, and the breaking-up started from the centre of the beam. Also, when the laser energy density is below another critical level, defined as E_{min} , the MMC layer will be less effectively incorporated. The relationship between the laser energy density and the degree of incorporation of the MMC layer with the base alloy, relative to the distance from the beam centre, is given schematically in Fig.6. The curves 1 and 2 in Fig.6 need to be neither straight lines nor parallel to each other. The relationship is thought to be applicable for both the situations of the preplaced SiC_p alone and the preplaced mixture, but the E_{max} and E_{min} values for the preplaced mixture should be greater than those for preplaced SiC_p alone, to compensate for a reduction of energy absorption due to a smaller addition of SiC_p in the preplaced layer. Using any levels of laser energy density between E_{max} and E_{min} , e.g. line 3 in Fig.6, will predict a certain width of MMC layer, and in the region $D_B < D_c$, this MMC layer is well incorporated with the surface, as shown in Figs.2 and 3. Beyond this well incorporated MMC region on both sides, (where $D_B > D_c$ is described in Fig.6), the MMC layer may still be continuous, but separated from the surface. It should be mentioned that the "poorly incorporated region" occurs at the bottom of the MMC, where the temperature is lowest, and the "broken MMC" starts at the top of the MMC, where the temperature is highest. When an excessively thick layer is preplaced, both a poorly incorporated region and a broken MMC may occur; therefore, the thickness of MMC must be optimised to avoid both these features.

Figure.6 A schematic relation between the laser energy density and the incorporation of MMC layer with the base alloy.

The relation shown schematically in Fig.6 is also applicable to the injection process. When a suitable level of E was used, a well incorporated region was produced at the beam centre, and a poorly incorporated region at the edge of the MMC, Fig.5. Increasing the laser energy density resulted in a very complex microstructure. This is shown in Fig.7. More SiC_p reacted with, or dissolved into, the matrix. Al_4SiC_4 (dark grey platelets), Al_4C_3 (black needles), and free silicon (grey particles) formed. The dark grey Al_4SiC_4 platelets were identified by EDX associated with TEM [5] and by X-ray diffractometry [18], as were the black Al_4C_3 needles [7, 18]. There are two areas in Fig.7. The one above the line Y-Z shows fewer SiC_p particles and more free Si and Al_4SiC_4 , and the region below Y-Z more SiC_p and Al_4C_3 needles. Since the upper area was closer to the laser, it would be expected that during the laser processing this area would be at a higher temperature than the area below Y-Z. At a high energy density, the same morphologies were obtained in the SiC_p preplacement technique reported previously [7], except that no cracks were found in the SiC_p within the preplaced MMC. These observations are in good agreement with the work by Viala et al [18], where Al_4C_3 was reported to form from liquid ($\text{L} \rightarrow \text{Al}_4\text{C}_3 + \text{SiC}$) in the temperature range 940 to 1620 K, and Al_4SiC_4 ($4\text{Al} + 4\text{SiC} \rightarrow \text{Al}_4\text{SiC}_4 + 3\text{Si}$) at temperatures higher or equal to 1670 K.

Figure.7 A typical microstructure obtained when a high laser energy density ($E=280 \text{ MJmm}^{-1}$) was used with the injection technique.

3.2.4 OVERLAPPING THE LASER TRACKS

To obtain a continuous and well incorporated MMC layer on the whole surface, the poorly incorporated region should be remelted and converted into a well incorporated region of the next laser track. Therefore the well incorporated region should be greater than or equal to half of the distance between two overlapped tracks, i.e. $D_2 \geq D_1/2$, where D_1 is the distance between the two overlapped tracks. Failure to meet this relation resulted in poorly incorporated regions on the surface [7]. D_c is determined by the laser processing conditions, the particle cladding techniques, the volume fraction of SiC_p and the thickness of the cladding materials. When D_c is known for a single laser track for a continuous MMC, $D_c \geq D_1/2$ should be used to design the percent overlapping of the laser tracks. Therefore, D_c is recommended as a parameter in modelling the laser cladding process.

An MMC layer $80\mu\text{m}$ thick and over 9 mm wide was produced by overlapping three laser tracks on a SiC_p preplaced specimen. SiC_p was well distributed and embedded in the MMC layer, which was smooth, uniformly thick and free of poorly incorporated regions. Overlapping the laser tracks also successfully produced a wide MMC on a specimen preplaced from a mixture of $\text{SiC}_p + \text{AA6061}$, and the resultant microstructure was the same as that in the centre area of an MMC produced by a single laser track [7].

When overlapping of laser tracks was used with the injection technique, the preliminary experiments undertaken in this study did not produce a satisfactory MMC layer. A large fraction of porosity existed in the overlapped area of two laser tracks. The porosity was thought to result

from the effect of the oxidized MMC surface of the first track during remelting. due to the unsuccessful design of the protection system. In the present experimental system, argon gas carrying the powder was used to shroud, and therefore to protect, the laser glazing surface. The laser treated area which has just moved from under the beam may be less efficiently protected by the gas, and therefore more easily oxidized. To obtain a well incorporated MMC by using the injection technique for overlapping laser tracks, a specific experimental system should be designed to protect the area already treated as well as the area being treated. Obviously a system which can protect the whole specimen would be desirable.

3.3 WEAR RESISTANCE

The wear data is shown in Fig.8. All the specimens with an MMC on the surface showed a significant increase in the abrasive wear resistance compared with the base alloy. The SiC_p preplaced specimens showed two distinct sections in their wear graphs: one of a low slope and the other of a high slope. The slopes of the wear graphs are defined as the wear rate (mg/m). Therefore, the first section of the graphs recorded the wear resistance of the MMC, and the second showed that when the MMC was worn away, the wear occurred in the base alloy matrix. The second section (from 850 m to 1000 m) of the solid line in graph 5 should be extended by the dotted line, as shown in Fig.8, adding a hypothetical value for one more testing point (at 950 m). Thus, the slopes of the second section of all the graphs would then show the same wear rate of the base alloy. Also, the ordinates of the first section of the graphs should be related to the thickness of the MMC layer. The lowest thickness of $80\mu\text{m}$ for the MMC shown in Fig.2, gave the lowest ordinate of the first section in Graph 2. The MMC with a similar thickness had the same ordinate in the first section of graphs 3 and 5. Graphs 2 and 3 show the same slope in their first sections, related to the same size and about same volume fraction of SiC_p in the MMC's. Graph 4 shows a transition region between the first and the second sections associated with a variable wear rate at different thickness of the MMC. This is attributed to the effects of a poor distribution of SiC_p , a non-uniform thickness of the MMC, and the phases formed in the molten zone during laser processing. The total wear resistance of the injected MMC was higher than that of the $6\mu\text{m}$ preplaced SiC_p MMC. This must result from the effect of a large size of the injected SiC_p providing a higher abrasive wear resistance, as the volume fraction of SiC_p was $57\text{v}\%$ for the $6\mu\text{m}$ SiC_p preplaced specimen and about $30\text{v}\%$ for the injected specimen. Graph 5 shows the highest wear resistance because of the high volume fraction of $45\mu\text{m}$ SiC_p which was in this case well distributed in the MMC layer. In addition, although the injected MMC contained a large size of SiC_p , the cracked SiC_p 's and the porosity in the MMC may have had a negative effect on the wear resistance.

Figure.8 Wear test results: graph 1 for the base alloy; graph 2 a $80\mu\text{m}$ thick MMC (SiC_p $6\mu\text{m}$, $60\text{v}\%$, preplacement), Fig.2; graph 3 a $200\mu\text{m}$ thick MMC (SiC_p $6\mu\text{m}$, $57\text{v}\%$, preplacement); graph 4 an MMC ($\text{SiC}_p \leq 150\mu\text{m}$, $30\text{v}\%$, injection), Fig.5; and graph 5 a $200\mu\text{m}$ thick MMC ($\text{SiC}_p \leq 45\mu\text{m}$, $57\text{v}\%$, preplacement), Fig.4.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Using either the preplacement or injection of SiC_p during CO_2 laser processing, an MMC layer was produced on the surface of AA6061 Al alloys, which significantly increased the abrasive wear resistance.
2. The preplacement technique can produce a very smooth surface, with a uniformly thick MMC layer after laser processing, while an uneven surface was one of the characteristic features of the injection technique which developed a non-uniformly thick MMC.
3. Overlapping laser tracks on the preplaced surface successfully produced a wide MMC, but the application of overlapping laser tracks with the injection technique required a more efficient protection system against the specimen oxidation than that used in this project.
4. The injection technique may have an advantage if the cracking of large SiC_p can be overcome and laser track overlapping employed.
5. During laser processing, both Al_4C_3 and Al_4SiC_4 phases may form in both the preplacement and the injection cases. Al_4SiC_4 is likely to form at higher temperatures than Al_4C_3 .
6. The width $2D_c$ of a well incorporated region produced by a single laser track is recommended as an important parameter in the overlapping process because the relation $D_c \geq D/2$ has to be satisfied to eliminate the poorly incorporated regions between overlapped laser tracks.

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REFERENCES

1. D. K. Das, A. G. Paradkar and R. S. Mishra, *Scripta Metall. Mater.* **26**, 1211-1214(1992).
2. K. Uenishi, A. Sugimoto and K. F. Kobayashi, *Z. Metallkd* **83**, 241-245(1992).
3. P. Sallamand and J. M. Pelletier, *Mater. Sci. Eng.* **A171**, 263-270(1993).
4. T. N. Baker, H. Xin, C. Hu and S. Mridha, *Mater. Sci. Tech.* **10**, 536-544(1994).
5. C. Hu and T. N. Baker, *J. Mater. Sci.* **30**, 891-897(1995).
6. C. Hu, L. Barnard, S. Mridha and T. N. Baker, *Adv. Proc. Mater.*, accepted for publication.
7. C. Hu, H. Xin and T. N. Baker, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, submitted for publication.
8. C. Hu, H. Xin and T. N. Baker, *J. Mater. Sci.*, submitted for publication.
9. K. P. Cooper and J. D. Ayers, *Surface Eng.* **1**, 263-272(1985).
10. C. W. Draper and J. M. Poate, *Inter. Met. Rev.* **30**, 85-108(1985).
11. J. H. Aboud and D. R. F. West, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* **9**, 308-310(1990).
12. G. Abbas and D. R. F. West, *Wear* **143**, 353-363(1991).
13. J. H. Abboud and D. R. F. West, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* **10**, 1149-1152(1991).
14. A. A. Wang, S. Sircar and J. Mazumder, *J. Mater. Sci.* **28**, 5113-5122(1993).
15. K. J. Bhansali and R. Mehrabian, *J. Metals* **9**, 30-34(1982).
16. F. M. Hosking, F. F. Portillo, R. Wunderlin and R. Mehrabian, *J. Mater. Sci.* **17**, 477-497(1982).
17. M. F. Ashby and K. E. Easterling, *Acta. Metall.* **32**, 1935-1948(1984).
18. J. C. Viala, P. Fortier and J. Bouix, *J. Mater. Sci.* **25**, 1842-1850(1990).